

ISic4376

Milestone of three Augusti

Language

Latin

Type

milestone

Material

limestone

Object

milestone

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Found on the route of the 'via Pompeia' at contrada Pistunina, to the south of Messina

Coordinates

38.147448, 15.527276

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Soprintendenza stores, inventory ME 28263

Physical Description

A fragment of a column miliaria

Dimensions

Height 35 cm

Width 33 cm

Depth 14 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letters are uneven, maximum height recorded

Letter heights:

Lines 1-6: 53 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. DDD(ominis) NNN(ostris)

2. Constantin(o)

3. et M, a, x, i, m, i, n, o

4.

5. ISSI, MTA

6. [---]

Apparatus

Text based upon photograph and drawing in La Torre and Toscano Raffa 2017
Liciniano?

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

La Torre, G.F., Toscano Raffa, A. 2017. Un miliario da Pistunina e brevi considerazioni sulla viabilità costiera ionica. In Tigano, G.(eds.), *Da Zancle a Messina 2016. Nuovi dati di archeologia urbana*. Palermo. pp. 179-184.

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Di Paola, Lucietta 2016. Il cursus publicus in età tardoantica: storia di un servizio di stato tra conservazione e mutamento. *Antiquité Tardive*. 24: 57-80. At 73-77, figs. 1-2

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